

1 **NLRP10 orchestrates barrier integrity in the skin.**

2 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹

3 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com

4 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467

5 East Islip, NY USA 11730

6 A basic function of the innate immune system is rapid defense during the period in which adaptive antigen
7 specific responses have not yet matured - for example, activation of the C-reactive protein and defensin
8 expression to protect barrier epithelial. A second basic function of the innate immune system is in
9 instruction of the adaptive immune system - in other words, adjuvanting appropriate immunological
10 defense against non-self (e.g., lipopolysaccharide-induced co-stimulatory molecule (e.g., B7) expression
11 to promote antigen specific immunoglobulin expression by facilitating immunological synapse contacts
12 between the adaptive immune cell (B or T cells) and innate immune cell (antigen presenting cell).
13 Activation of the innate immune system is orchestrated by two major gene families, the toll-like receptors
14 (TLRs) and Nod-like receptors (NLRs).

15 NLR family member genes are classically understood as pattern recognition receptors (NOD2) and
16 inflammasome components (NLRP3) but are also likely to possess functions independent of microbial
17 defense, like in reproductive biology associated with maternal effect in the embryo. We have described the
18 transcriptional and cellular functions of the Crohn's Disease susceptibility gene *NOD2*. We recently
19 described the inflammasome associated gene *NLRC4* as an inhibitor of the anti-viral interferon signaling
20 pathway. We previously described a novel cellular function for an NLR gene product, wherein activation of
21 the NLR family gene *NLRP10* was found in cellular contexts associated with high cell cycle speed,
22 including feedback from nutritional (amino acid) sensors and cycling-associated plasma membrane
23 phospholipid activity. We recently described immunological functions of NLRP10 characterized by
24 regulation of CD40, ICOSLG, and BAFF-R signaling, as well as a hyper activation of IL-10 and AHR
25 resulting from NLRP10 deficiency, indicating NLRP10 can serve to facilitate non-self defense by the
26 adaptive immune system (B-cell) and to regulate tolerogenic responses.

27 We describe here cellular functions of NLRP10 in protection of barrier integrity. NLRP10 controls
28 expression of caspase 14, a caspase with restricted expression in terminally differentiated epidermis that
functions to process filaggrin. We found among NLRP10 targets multiple kallikreins, a steroid enzyme that
functions in ceramide biochemistry, keratins with described immunoregulatory properties, and late
cornfield envelope genes. Several of the molecules we describe here as NLRP10 targets are susceptibility
genes for skin disease in humans, including pachyonychia congenita, ichthyosis vulgaris, psoriasis and
Netherton syndrome. *NLRP10* was activated by injury in the skin, and its expression was regulated during
keratinocyte differentiation in vitro. NLR family genes possess both classically understood immunological
functions in adjuvanting adaptive responses and rapid non-specific defense, as well as less well
understood functions that promote tissue-specific defense but are based on control of cell biologic
components of the cell.